

Book review of: Seda Yilmaz Wörfel, “Adverbial Relations in Turkish-German Bilingualism” Münster, New York 2022: Waxmann Verlag GmbH, pp. 265;

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Abstract

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Keywords

Language, Turkish, German, multilingual, bilingual, diaspora, upbringing, practices, culture

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Adverbial Relations in Turkish-German Bilingualism is a book by Seda Yılmaz Wörfel, a doctor of German linguistics at the University of Potsdam and research associate at the Mercator-Institute for Literacy and Language Education at the University of Cologne. It presents the sociolinguistic development of Turkish-German bilinguals and the way it influences the use of adverbial clause-combining constructions.

The book presents an interesting panorama of language learning by bilingual people, especially adverbial clause-combining constructions, and factors which appear in it. Learning is viewed as a dynamic process, that is why it requires a lot of aspects to occur in order to enable progress. *Adverbial Relations in Turkish-German Bilingualism* is a book addressed to a wide audience of readers interested in understanding and developing the process of language acquisition, particularly of German and Turkish. Various groups, especially teachers and students can benefit from reading this study.

The book contains eight chapters. In the first chapter, the author presents the context in which bilingual German-born Turks learn languages they use on a daily basis (L1: Turkish and L2: German). The second chapter is devoted to the dynamics of specificity of learning by bilingual people. Being bilingual is not simply about speaking well two languages, but rather about possessing a specific linguistic pattern which consist of various competences, such as metalinguistic awareness, being creative in language learning strategies or sound knowledge, and cognitive control mechanisms. According to the theory applied by the author, there are more factors which influence a learning process. These are divided into: internal (self-confidence, anxiety, motivation, etc.) and external ones (e.g., parental background). The interaction between these elements is necessary to make an improvement in learning possible.

The following chapter discusses the expression of adverbial relations in Turkish and German, adverbial clause-combining strategies in Turkish forms of adverbial subordination in German, and presents grammatical context for the research. The next chapter presents key differences between orality and literacy acquisition of language, the role of genre (narration or expository) and the importance of information density in expressing adverbial relations. The subsequent two chapters describe previous research on the use of clause-combining constructions by Turkish bilinguals, its implications, and the methodology of the present study.

The author focuses on developmental change in the use of adverbial clause-combining constructions in Turkish (L1) and German (L2) and wants to answer the following questions: 1) How does the use of adverbial clause-combining constructions in Turkish and German change over time in the 7th, 10th and 12th grades in written and spoken contexts? 2) What kinds of cross-linguistic transfer can be identified in the use of adverbial clause-combining constructions in L1 and L2? and 3) What is the role of sociolinguistic factors in the production of adverbial clause-combining constructions in written and spoken contexts?

The study has shown progress in the use of adverbial clause-combining constructions in both L1 and L2 and that the participants use more integrative expressions and various converbal constructions and/or nominalizations in Turkish and numerous types of connectors in German. The influence of extra-linguistic factors on the development of adverbial clause-combining constructions used per sentence was found in Turkish but not in German. These factors are age, parental education, media use, and participation in L1 instruction courses.

The mutual influence between Turkish and German was noticed, for example participants who use adverbial clause-combining constructions in their L2, also use more adverbial constructions

in their L1. However, some differences were indicated, for instance in German more types of adverbial clause-combining constructions were used than in Turkish, but with lower frequencies per type. What is interesting, the use of adverbial clause-combining constructions is rather dynamic, rather than stable and linear. In other words, it is not enough to learn diverse and elaborate constructions at a certain age, to be able to use them in the years that follow. For instance, in German some of these constructions (for example, ‘as long as’) are used in the 10th grade, but do not appear at all in the 12th grade among survey participants.

What is more, competences may be also transferred within one language and across different modes. It was noticed that most of the participants who achieved a higher level in writing also achieved a higher discourse ability level in speech.

To conclude, the analysis has shown that the older bilinguals become, the more integrated constructions they use and the more adverbial clause-combining constructions per sentence they tend to apply in both Turkish and German. It is worth mentioning that the participants use more adverbial clause-combining constructions per sentence in the oral form than in text. I recommend the book to the community of linguists, socio-linguists, sociologists of language, psychologists, educators and policy makers.